
Language Attitudes of Foreign Students Learning Indonesian: A Study at 'In-Country Learning Program BIPAS, Udayana University, Bali'

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Abstract

This study focuses on analysing the language attitudes of students studying Indonesian as a foreign language on the Bipas in-country learning programme at Udayana University in Bali. The study particularly investigates whether the language attitudes of foreign students learning Indonesian on the programme change by the end of the course. The study involved 38 foreign students and 5 Indonesian lecturers in the Spring 2024 semester. Survey techniques and interviews were used to collect the data. The results show that despite the Balinese community's maximum support for students using the Indonesian language, their attitudes towards Indonesian language undergo positive changes from the beginning to the end of the course. The affective and conative dimensions are especially clear in this, as well as in their perception of how easy learning is. However, the cognitive dimension related to career value remains relatively low.

1. Introduction

The Indonesian government is currently promoting the internationalisation of higher education in an effort to establish world-class universities in the country. Various efforts are being made to achieve this, including encouraging an increase in the number of foreign students studying in Indonesia. Bali is a popular destination for foreign students in Indonesia and is also one of the world's most famous tourist destinations. The initial survey conducted for this study found that students choose Bali for its natural beauty, unique culture, social interaction and strong international atmosphere, which provides a different perspective in line with each student's educational needs.

There are approximately 52 public and private universities spread across the island. Udayana University is one of these and is the largest and most renowned university on the island.

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The university offers several international study programmes, including the Bali International Programme on Asian Studies (BIPAS), where this research was conducted. BIPAS is an interdisciplinary programme offering thirteen courses across various disciplines each semester, including economics, business, communication, tourism, the environment, engineering, cross-cultural studies and the Indonesian language. The Indonesian language course is a compulsory subject for all international students on the programme.

Recognising that international students come to the island not only for academic purposes, and located on an island renowned as a global tourist destination, BIPAS has deliberately designed its international programme to balance study time with leisure time for its students. Campus-based learning takes place only three days a week (Monday to Wednesday), leaving students with the opportunity to enjoy the natural beauty and explore the island on the other days. Preliminary observations indicate that the programme's learning design has had two main impacts: Firstly, it has successfully attracted more international students to the programme. Secondly, it has presented a unique challenge to administrators, and particularly lecturers teaching Indonesian language classes, in terms of enhancing students' motivation to learn and their language attitudes while they are enjoying their holiday in Bali.

Regarding the role of learning motivation and language attitudes in foreign language learning, experts argue that both variables are crucial to students' success (Wlodowski, 1985; McGroarty, 1996; Rost; Dörnyei, 2006; Anjomshua & Firooz, 2015). One of the most famous studies in this area was conducted by Robert Gardner and colleagues in 1959. This study questioned why some students were able to learn quickly and achieve high results, while others, despite being given the same opportunity, failed. They concluded that, in addition to intellectual capacity and talent, language attitude also plays an important role in students' learning achievements. This factor is said to influence another important factor: learning motivation. Students' attitudes towards the language being learnt affect their success in second language learning. If their attitudes are positive, they will be more motivated to learn the target language; if they are negative, however, they will become demotivated (1985).

This article focuses specifically on research into the language attitudes of foreign students learning Indonesian in the Bipas programme at Udayana University. In the context of this research, the programme is referred to as an in-country learning programme, as foreign students learn Indonesian in Indonesia (Bali).

Furthermore, to determine the extent of students' attitudes towards language, a survey was conducted in 2018 of 76 foreign students studying on one of Udayana University's international programmes. It was found that their attitudes towards language tended to be negative: (1) 81% of students stated that they came to Bali to study and holiday; (2) all commented that they took Indonesian language courses only because they were mandatory; and (3) 65% said that Indonesian language skills would not help them in their future careers. In fact, five students wrote in the comments that they did not need to speak Indonesian in Bali because almost everyone they met seemed to understand and speak English. This illustrates that, in addition to the subject being studied, students' language attitudes also depend on who is learning the language and "where" it is learned.

Based on the above background information, two issues were identified: (1) What are the language attitudes of foreign students learning Indonesian on the BIPAS in-country learning programme at Udayana University? (2). Do students' language attitudes change at the end of the course?

2. Literature Review

2.1. Language Attitude

Attitude is one of the affective variables that is frequently studied in second/foreign language acquisition (Sparks & Ganschow, 2001). The term 'attitude' refers to the basic natural ability to perform an action, aptitude for action, or tendency towards a particular action. Anderson (1974: 47) distinguishes between two types of attitude: language and non-language. Non-language attitudes include political, social, and aesthetic attitudes, among others. Meanwhile, language attitudes are often defined as psychological phenomena that form part of attitudes in general. Language attitudes are evaluative reactions towards a particular language (Fishman, 1966), representing mental positions or feelings towards a language or the people/society that use it (Kridalaksana, 2001: 197).

In his early research on motivation, Gardner (1959) identified language attitude as a key factor in successful second language acquisition. He claimed that attitude and motivation often occur together in individuals learning a second language. He stated that learners' attitudes towards the target culture would impact their level of success when learning a second language. "The words, sounds, grammatical principles and so on that the language teacher tries to present are more than just aspects of a linguistic code; they are integral parts of another culture." Consequently, students' attitudes towards the specific language group influence how successful they are in incorporating aspects of that language" (Gardner, 1985:6). The importance of attitude in second language learning lies in the idea that positive attitudes towards the target culture will motivate students to learn the target language, while negative attitudes will have the opposite effect. If learners like the language they are learning, they will be motivated to learn it; if they do not like it, they will be reluctant.

Language attitudes can be useful for language teaching and planning. A person learning a language is motivated by their attitude towards it. These attitudes include 1) how they feel about the practical purposes of using the target language and 2) how they feel about people who use the target language (Spolsky, 1989: 149). The language attitudes of language users, whether bilingual or multilingual, manifest as feelings of pride or derision and acceptance or rejection of particular languages and language communities. These feelings apply to the languages mastered by individuals and to members of the community. These attitudes are related to the status of language in society, including its political and economic status. Similarly, language use is often stereotypically associated with the life of a particular community because language is a means of communication and a social identity (Rusyana, 1989: 31–32).

2.2 Components of Language Attitude.

The attitude that an individual shows towards a language has a structure consisting of several components. There are two different approaches to these components. The first states that attitude, including language attitude, is a combination of three conceptually different reactions to a particular object. These three components are: (1) the cognitive component, relating to beliefs, opinions and evaluations of the attitude object; (2) the affective component, relating to emotions such as love, hate, liking or disliking the attitude object; and (3) the conative component, relating to behaviour and tendencies towards action. In contrast, the second approach considers the affective component to be the only relevant indicator of attitude, meaning that only one term is required: 'affect' or 'feeling'. This study refers to the three components of attitude introduced by Lambert (1967) and Eagly and Chaiken (1993). The following is a description of these experts' theories:

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2.2.1 Components of Attitude According to Lambert (1967)

Lambert (1967) states that attitudes, including language attitudes, consist of three components: cognitive, affective and conative. The cognitive component relates to knowledge of the surrounding environment and to ideas typically used in the thinking process. It is related to knowledge, views, and beliefs about the object of the attitude, obtained through seeing, hearing, and feeling. From a linguistic perspective, this component relates to the linguistic insight possessed by the speaker, enabling them to choose appropriate language variations for the situation.

Meanwhile, the affective component relates to an individual's emotional response to something, involving positive or negative evaluations of an object or situation. If someone likes something, they are said to have a positive attitude towards it. If the opposite is true, they are said to have a negative attitude. The conative component is defined as an individual's tendency to behave in a certain way towards an object, or in other words, it relates to behaviour or actions as the 'final decision' in response to a situation. This component of attitude can be seen through the subject's observable actions or behaviour.

2.2.2 Components of Attitude According to Eagly and Chaiken (1993).

As attitudes are internal and hypothetical, they cannot be directly observed, but must be inferred and evaluated through individuals' responses to a stimulus. They argue that individuals' responses to stimuli can be categorised as cognitive, affective or behavioural. Evaluative responses of the cognitive class are often referred to as 'beliefs', which include the associations and connections people make between attitude objects and various attributes (p. 11). Thus, the cognitive component can be defined as beliefs about what is and isn't true regarding the attitude object.

Meanwhile, evaluative responses of the affective type include feelings and emotions, such as enjoyment of a poem written in Japanese. The affective component of an attitude can also be demonstrated through "sympathetic nervous system activity" experienced by a person when confronted with a particular attitude object (p. 11). For example, some people may feel emotional or angry when they see a nuclear power plant, while others may feel hope and optimism. The affective component of an attitude is often the focus of attitude research investigations (Fishbein, 1967: 257) and is becoming increasingly important due to its close relationship with the cognitive component (Garrett et al., 2003: 10). Garrett et al. (2003: 10) explain that, although beliefs (i.e. the cognitive component) are free of affective content, they can be based on, or even lead to, affective reactions. Therefore, attitude researchers must consider both people's beliefs (the cognitive component) and their feelings (the affective component) towards the attitude object.

Behaviour is the third component of attitude and is also referred to as the 'conative', 'behavioural' or 'action' component (Eagley & Chaiken, 1993: 12; Fishbein, 1967: 259). According to these authors, this component leads to actual actions and can reflect a person's behavioural intentions. Therefore, behavioural responses do not necessarily result in actual behaviour, but may merely indicate an individual's intention to act. Consequently, the behavioural component is considered to be a tendency to perform certain actions towards the attitude object.

3. Research Methodology

This study was conducted within the BIPAS international programme at Udayana University. It applied the explanatory sequential mixed method design (Creswell, 2014), consisting of two

phases: quantitative and qualitative. In the quantitative phase, 38 Indonesian language students from the Spring 2024 semester (February–May 2024) were recruited as respondents. They completed two identical questionnaires at two different times: one at the beginning of the course and the other at the end. This technique was employed to identify relevant data by measuring students' language attitudes. These components were introduced by Lambert (1967) and Eagley and Chaiken (1993): 1) the cognitive component, which identified how students evaluated Indonesian as a foreign language and whether they considered it important; 2) the affective component, which identified students' feelings towards Indonesian and whether they liked it; and 3) the conative component, which identified their tendency to act towards Indonesian and whether they were inclined to accept or reject the language. Each subscale in the questionnaire consisted of statements rated on a 1–6 Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 6 = Strongly Agree). The results of the first and second questionnaire completions were analysed using SPSS 22 for Windows and compared to determine whether students' attitudes towards the language changed during the semester. Here is the interval, score and category of the results:

Interval Score	Category
$x \leq 2.25$	Very Low
$2.25 < x \leq 3.08$	Low
$3.08 < x \leq 3.92$	Moderate
$3.92 < x \leq 4.75$	High
$x > 4.75$	Very High

In the qualitative phase, group interviews were conducted with students and five Indonesian language lecturers. This technique was chosen in order to prevent repetitive information collected from respondents. Additionally, placing participants in groups enabled them to ask each other questions and explain their responses. The interview questions included further enquiries about the students' attitudes towards language while studying in Bali, as well as their views on and experiences of learning in the country. The data collected through these interviews was used to supplement the limited information provided by the survey results.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1.1 Language Attitudes of Students at the Beginning of the Course

To determine the language attitudes of Bipas foreign students towards Indonesian at the beginning of the academic year, a questionnaire was completed by 38 Bipas foreign students on the Spring 2024 programme. The following is an overview of their average language attitude scores:

4.1. Average Language Attitude Scores of Students at the Beginning of the Course.

Indicator	Item	Mean
sk1	Learning Indonesian is very great	4.13
sk2	I really enjoy learning Indonesian	2.82
sk3	Indonesian is a very important part of the course program	3.08
sk4	I plan to learn as much Indonesian as possible	2.97
sk5	I think Indonesian is efficient	2.87
sk6	I think being able to speak Indonesian reflects intellectuality	2.89

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sk7	Able to speak Indonesian reflects modernity	3.11
sk8	I believe Indonesian is easy I learned regularly	3.08
sk9	I believe that by mastering Indonesian, it will be easy to get a job	2.61
sk10	I believe that Indonesian will one day have an important role in the world	2.87
sk11	I try to improve my Indonesian language skills	4.58
sk12	I try to pronounce Indonesian words like a native speaker	3.26
sk13	I feel challenged to learn Indonesian	2.89
sk14	I feel more confident after learning Indonesian	2.66
Mean total		3.13

At the beginning of the lecture, the average attitude of students was 3.13, which is in the moderate category. Indicator SK9, 'I believe that by mastering Indonesian, it will be easy to get a job', had the lowest average score (2.61). This indicates that, at the beginning of the semester, students were less likely to agree that their Indonesian language skills would make it easier for them to find a job. They also tended to reject the idea that they would become more confident after learning Indonesian, with an average score of 2.66. Judging by the average score of 2.82 for category SK2, 'I really enjoy learning Indonesian', they did not particularly enjoy learning Indonesian at the beginning of their studies. However, students realise that learning Indonesian is beneficial, as indicated by an average score of 4.13 for SK1, 'Learning Indonesian is great', and they continue to strive to improve their Indonesian language skills while studying and living in Indonesia, as indicated by an average score of 4.58 for SK11, 'I try to improve my Indonesian language skills'.

4.1.2 Students' Attitudes Towards Language at the end of the Course

To determine students' attitudes towards language at the end of the course, 38 international students on the Bipas Spring Programme 2024 were asked to complete a questionnaire containing the same statements as those given at the beginning of the course. The following are the results of the average language attitude scores:

Table 4.2.

Average Language Attitude Scores of Students at the End of the Course.

Indicator	Item	Mean
sk1	Learning Indonesian is very great	5.33
sk2	I really enjoy learning Indonesian	5.44
sk3	Indonesian is a very important part of the course program	4.72
sk4	I plan to learn as much Indonesian as possible	4.61
sk5	I think Indonesian is efficient	4.28
sk6	I think being able to speak Indonesian reflects intellectuality	4.22
sk7	Able to speak Indonesian reflects modernity	4.17
sk8	I believe Indonesian is easy I learned regularly	5.00
sk9	I believe that by mastering Indonesian, it will be easy to get a job	3.44

Indicator	Item	Mean
sk10	I believe that Indonesian will one day have an important role in the world	3.33
sk11	I try to improve my Indonesian language skills	4.94
sk12	I try to pronounce Indonesian words like a native speaker	5.06
sk13	I feel challenged to learn Indonesian	5.06
sk14	I feel more confident after learning Indonesian	4.67
Mean Total		4.59

By the end of the course, students' attitudes towards the language had improved significantly, with an average score of 4.59 (high category). Indicator 12 and 13, 'I try to pronounce Indonesian words like a native speaker' and 'I feel challenged to learn Indonesian', respectively, achieved the highest average score of 5.06. This suggests that, after studying Indonesian for one semester in the Bipas programme, students want to be able to pronounce Indonesian words like locals and are motivated to learn the language. However, the average scores for statements sk10 and sk9, which ask whether students believe that Indonesian will one day play an important role in the world and whether mastering Indonesian will make it easier for them to find employment, are 3.33 and 3.44 respectively. This indicates that students are still not very confident that Indonesian will play an important role in the future or that mastering the language will make it easier for them to find employment.

4.1.3. Comparison of Questionnaire data on the Students' Attitudes towards Indonesian at the Beginning and End of the course.

To determine whether there was a change in students' language attitudes at the beginning compared to the end of the course, an analysis was conducted to compare the average scores for each statement in the distributed questionnaire. The results of the comparison are shown in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3.

Comparison of Language Attitudes of Students at the Beginning and End of the Course.

Indicator	Item	Mean at Beginning of Course	Mean at End of Course	The Change
sk1	Learning Indonesian is very great	4.13	5.33	1.20
sk2	I really enjoy learning Indonesian	2.82	5.44	2.63
sk3	Indonesian is a very important part of the course program	3.08	4.72	1.64
sk4	I plan to learn as much Indonesian as possible	2.97	4.61	1.64
sk5	I think Indonesian is efficient	2.87	4.28	1.41
sk6	I think being able to speak Indonesian reflects intellectuality	2.89	4.22	1.33
sk7	Able to speak Indonesian reflects modernity	3.11	4.17	1.06

Indicator	Item	Mean at Beginning of Course	Mean at End of Course	The Change
sk8	I believe Indonesian is easy I learned regularly	3.08	5.00	1.92
sk9	I believe that by mastering Indonesian, it will be easy to get a job	2.61	3.44	0.84
sk10	I believe that Indonesian will one day have an important role in the world	2.87	3.33	0.46
sk11	I try to improve my Indonesian language skills	4.58	4.94	0.37
sk12	I try to pronounce Indonesian words like a native speaker	3.26	5.06	1.79
sk13	I feel challenged to learn Indonesian	2.89	5.06	2.16
sk14	I feel more confident after learning Indonesian	2.66	4.67	2.01
Mean Total		3.13	4.59	1.46

As shown in Table 4.3 above, there has been an increase in the average score for each statement. SK2, 'I really enjoy learning Indonesian', has seen the highest increase, at 2.63. This indicates that, by the end of the course, students enjoyed learning Indonesian more, which boosted their confidence. The statement 'I feel more confident after learning Indonesian' (sk14) saw an average increase of 2.01. When viewed from the perspective of the cognitive component of language attitude, the average scores of the students are as follows:

Diagram 4.1:
Comparison of the Cognitive Component of Students' Language Attitude at the Beginning and End of the Course

As shown in Diagram 4.1, each statement point experienced an increase in average value. Statement point sk12, 'I try to pronounce Indonesian words like a native speaker', experienced the most significant increase, at 1.79. Initially in the low language attitude category (2.97), this statement point increased to the high category (4.61) by the end of the course. This indicates that, by the end of the course, students were trying harder to pronounce Indonesian words like locals. Meanwhile, statement sk11, 'I try to improve my Indonesian language skills,' had the lowest average score increase, at 0.37. However, as Figure 4.1 shows, students had already made considerable efforts to master Indonesian by the time they began their studies on the Bipas programme at Udayana University. This is reflected in the initial average score for statement sk11, which was 4.58, increasing to 4.94 by the end of the programme.

Meanwhile, when viewed from the affective component, the improvement in students' language attitudes at the end of the course is illustrated in the diagram below:

Diagram 4.2:
Comparison of the Affective Components of Students' Language Attitudes at the Beginning and End of the Course.

In terms of affective attitude, most students' attitude towards the Indonesian language is at level 5, indicating that they like the language a lot. Comparing the average scores for each statement at the beginning and end of the course revealed a significant increase, particularly for statements sk2 ('I really enjoy learning Indonesian'), sk13 ('I feel challenged to learn Indonesian') and sk14 ('I feel more confident after learning Indonesian'), with respective increases of 2.63, 2.16 and 2.01. Initially, these three statements were in the low category, but they increased and moved into the high category by the end of the course. Meanwhile, statement SK1, 'Learning Indonesian is great', also increased. Initially, the average score for this statement was 4.13, which is in the high category, and this increased to 5.33. This indicates that students are increasingly aware that learning Indonesian is beneficial.

Finally, diagram 4.3 below illustrates students' language attitude in terms of the final component of language: the conative component.

*Diagram 4.3:
Comparison of the Conative Component of Students' Language Attitude at the Beginning and End of the Course.*

In terms of attitude, students' views on the Indonesian language showed a significant improvement. At the beginning of the course, their views were in the low category (total mean: 2.99), but then increased to the high category (total mean: 4.42). This improvement indicates that they recognise the efficiency and intellectuality of Indonesian, and that it is not difficult to learn with regular practice (sk5, 6, 7 and 8).

Quantitatively, the analysis of the above data shows that students' attitudes towards learning the Indonesian language changed significantly between the beginning and end of the course. This is evident in the diagram 4.4 below:

*Diagram 4.4:
Language Attitude Improvement at the End of the Course*

As shown in Diagram 4.4, students' attitudes towards the Indonesian language improved in all three components by the end of the course. The affective component experienced the highest increase in average score, rising from 2.00 (moderate) to 3.00 (high). This was followed by the conative component's language attitude, which increased from 1.43 (low) to 2.87 (high). The cognitive component increased by 1.13, rising from moderate to high. These figures suggest that by the end of the Bipas programme, students had grown to like the Indonesian language more, had become more accepting of it, and had become more aware of its importance in their lives.

These quantitative results are reinforced by qualitative data from student interviews. Students revealed that they felt happier using Indonesian after interacting with the local community. One respondent stated:

'I guess they're all friendly, but when you speak to them, they become even friendlier. It becomes a lot more fun... it's just nicer to interact with them" (Student 9).

This demonstrates that social interactions outside the classroom foster positive attitudes towards the language

These findings are supported by interviews with lecturers. Initially, lecturers observed that students tended to be passive and unenthusiastic, particularly when the focus was on grammatical structures or formal grammar. However, after students began to experience using Indonesian in everyday life in Bali, their attitudes changed, becoming more active and positive.

"Initially, they were rather passive, but once they started interacting with the local community, they became much more engaged in using Indonesian in class" (Lecturer 1).

"They seemed happy when they could converse with local people. It gave them confidence and made the lessons feel more meaningful" (Lecturer 2).

From both students' and lecturers' perspectives, social factors such as familiarity with the local community and enjoyment of practical exercises outside the classroom were more effective in fostering positive attitudes towards Indonesian than academic motivation or career prospects.

However, when asked about the dominant language used when communicating with the local community, students stated that, as a tourist area where some members of the community are able to communicate in English, Bali does not actually support the frequent use of the Indonesian language. Interviews revealed that the local community still frequently uses English when communicating with foreign students, which leads students to also use English. This is reflected in the following statement from one student, which was supported by other student respondents: "I use English when communicating with the local community." Lecturers observed similar conditions, stating that, although the social environment is friendly and supportive,

Indonesian is not always used consistently in daily interactions. This makes it difficult for students to continue practising Indonesian outside the classroom. As one lecturer stated: 'The social environment in Bali is very friendly and supportive, but the language used in daily interactions is often a mixture of English and Indonesian, so students need to be more proactive in using Indonesian' (Lecturer 3)

Nevertheless, students said that they find it easier to learn Indonesian in Bali than in their home countries, where the local community does not use the language in everyday communication.

When asked whether Indonesian would support their future careers, most students answered 'no'.

'No.' All of them shook their heads when asked. 'But I think it depends. If you're going to work for an Asian company, then maybe yes' (Student 7).

The discussion above leads us to a view that a gap remains in their language attitudes, particularly with regard to the cognitive component. Both quantitative data and interview results suggest that Indonesian is not yet perceived as a valuable asset for their global careers. The belief that Indonesian could support their careers or hold a strategic position in the international arena has not yet become the primary motivation for most students. This is evident from the low average scores on the indicator of belief in the future usefulness of Indonesian in both the quantitative data and the interview results. Students tend to view Indonesian as a language that is only relevant in local or regional contexts, rather than global ones.

5. Conclusion

From the above discussion, it can be concluded that despite the Balinese community's maximum support for students using the Indonesian language, their attitudes towards language undergo positive changes from the beginning to the end of the course. This is particularly evident in the affective and conative dimensions, as well as in their perception of how easy learning is. However, the cognitive dimension related to career value remains relatively low. This suggests that, although the Indonesian language learning programme has successfully fostered positive social and emotional attitudes, it has not yet fully succeeded in developing a strategic perception of the value of language in a global context.

Overall, students' attitudes towards Indonesian change depending on the situation and are influenced by their direct social experiences during the learning process, particularly through interactions with local communities outside the classroom. Students tend to develop positive attitudes when they experience the practical benefits of using Indonesian in everyday situations. Such interactions foster self-confidence, emotional closeness and a sense of belonging to the language, impacting their affective and conative attitudes towards it.

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References

- Anderson, E. A. (1974). *Language attitude, belief, and values: A study in linguistic cognitive frameworks*. Washington, DC: Georgetown University.
- Anjomshoa, L., & Firooz, S. (2015). The importance of motivation in second language learning. *International Journal on Studies in English Language and Literature*, 3(2), 126–137. <https://www.arcjournals.org/pdfs/ijsell/v3-i2/12.pdf> (Retrieved March 6, 2020)
- Dörnyei, Z., Csizér, K., & Németh, N. (2006). *Motivation, language attitudes, and globalization: A Hungarian perspective*. Clevedon, UK: Multilingual Matters.
- Dörnyei, Z. (2008). New ways of motivating foreign language learners: Generating visions. *Links*, 38(3–4). <http://www.cilt.org.uk/publications/bulletins/links> (Retrieved March 25, 2020)
- Fishman, J. A. (1966). *Language loyalty in the United States*. The Hague, Netherlands: Mouton.
- Gardner, R. C. (1985). *Social psychology and second-language learning: The role of attitudes and motivation*. London, England: Edward Arnold.
- Gardner, R. C. (2010). *Motivation and second language acquisition: The socio-educational model*. New York, NY: Peter Lang Publishing.
- Gardner, R. C., & Lambert, W. E. (1972). *Attitudes and motivation in second-language learning*. Rowley, MA: Newbury House Publishers.
- Kridalaksana, H. (2001). *Kamus linguistik*. Jakarta, Indonesia: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Lambert, W. E. (1967). A social psychology of bilingualism. *Journal of Social Issues*, 23(2), 91–109. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4560.1967.tb00578.x>
- Spolsky, B., & Hult, F. M. (Eds.). (2008). *The handbook of educational linguistics*. Oxford, UK: Blackwell Publishing.
- McGroarty, M. (1996). Language attitudes, motivation, and standards. In S. L. McKay & N. H. Hornberger (Eds.), *Sociolinguistics and language teaching* (pp. 3–46). Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
- Rusyana, Y. (1989). *Bahasa dan sastra dalam gamitan pendidikan*. Bandung, Indonesia: C.V. Diponegoro.
- Eagly, A. H., & Chaiken, S. (1993). *The psychology of attitudes*. Fort Worth, TX: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich College Publishers.
- Sparks, R., & Ganschow, L. (2001). Aptitude for learning a foreign language. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, 21, 90–111. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/231902873_Aptitude_for_learning_a_foreign_language (Retrieved February 2, 2021)
- Wlodkowski, R. J. (1985). *Enhancing adult motivation to learn*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.